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Efficacy of Vyoshadi Yoga in the Management of Udarashoola: A Pediatric Case Report

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Infantile colic, clinically known as *Udarashoola*, is a common condition affecting infants, characterized by excessive crying, abdominal discomfort, and disrupted sleep. This case report evaluates the efficacy of the Ayurvedic formulation, *Vyoshadi Yoga*, in managing *Udarashoola* in a 3-month-old exclusively breastfed male infant.

Methods: A 3-month-old infant, presenting with excessive crying, abdominal distension, back arching, facial flushing, and disturbed sleep for 10 days, was diagnosed with *Udarashoola* using classical Ayurvedic diagnostic signs, including *Stana dwesha* and *Mukhasweda*. The infant was administered 125 mg of *Vyoshadi Yoga* mixed with honey twice daily post-feeding for 14 days. Outcome measures were based on changes in pain episodes, duration of spasms, sleep patterns, abdominal rigidity, and gurgling sounds.

Results: After 14 days of treatment, there was a ~66% reduction in pain frequency and duration. Awakenings were reduced by 67%, and abdominal rigidity improved by 75%. Gurgling sounds also decreased. No adverse effects were reported during the treatment period.

Discussion: The results suggest that *Vyoshadi Yoga* is effective in alleviating the symptoms of infantile colic,

with minimal side effects. This case supports the potential use of *Vyoshadi Yoga* as a therapeutic option for pediatric care, particularly in treating *Udarashoola*.

Conclusion: *Vyoshadi Yoga* appears to be a safe and effective treatment for *Udarashoola*, offering significant symptom relief in a pediatric case with no adverse effects. Further studies are needed to confirm its broader applicability.

Keywords: Infantile Colic, *Udarashoola*, *Vyoshadi Yoga*, Ayurvedic Medicine, Pediatric Care, Infant Treatment

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Introduction

Ayurveda is recognized as the most scientifically grounded traditional medicinal system. Historically, it was divided into eight core branches (*Ashtanga*). Among these, *Kaumarabhritya*—also referred to as *Kaumartantra* or *Balachikitsa*—is especially important. This branch focuses on care before birth, during the postpartum period, and treatment of childhood illnesses.

During fetal development, the unborn child depends entirely on the mother's body. After birth, the infant must quickly undergo major adjustments in the respiratory, circulatory, digestive, and urinary systems to survive independently. Of these, the digestive system plays a crucial role, as proper digestion supports growth, tissue building, and overall development. However, digestive imbalances—like gas, indigestion, and colic—can occur in infancy and can adversely affect growth and weight gain.

Acharya Kashyapa's Kashyapa Samhita—particularly the chapter "*Vedanadhyaya*" in *Sutra Sthana*—provides a detailed and distinctive treatment of such pediatric issues. With this section, he laid down a strong foundation for clinical pediatrics in

Ayurveda, offering systematic guidance for examining and diagnosing illnesses in infants and children who are unable to clearly express their symptoms.

Infantile colic, known in modern pediatrics as prolonged and inconsolable crying in otherwise healthy babies, typically begins around 2–3 weeks of age and often subsides by 4–6 months. While conventional medicine frequently labels its cause as idiopathic, *Ayurveda* offers a deeper explanation—termed ***Udarashoola***—rooted in the imbalance of ***Vata dosha***, particularly within the delicate digestive fire (*agni*) of an infant.

Samprapti Of Udarashoola

Infant *Mandagni* (Low Digestive Strength) Developing *Dhatus* (Immature Tissues)

Aggravation of Vata in Gastrointestinal Tract

Pathophysiological Effects

- Gastrointestinal spasms
- Excessive gas buildup
- Gripping cries

Symptom Complex

- Abdominal distension & stiffness
- Arching of back
- Clenched fists
- Refusal to feed
- Flushing of face
- Inconsolable crying

The disease infantile colic can be comparable with ***Udarashoola*** described in Ayurvedic classics with the features described as ***Sthana Vyudasyate*** (rejects breast), ***Rauti*** (cries), ***Uttana Schava Bajyate*** (supine sleeping), ***Udara Stabdata*** (stiffness of the abdomen), ***Shaityam*** (coldness), ***Mukhasweda*** (perspiration of the face). Other texts described; the significant factor responsible for the genesis of *Shoola* is ***Vata (Vayu)***. ***Vayu*** presents in the body and gets aggravated because of different etiological factors, producing violent cutting & spasmodic pain in the abdominal cavity (*Kosta*). The

patient complains of pain as if he is being pierced with a pear (*Shanku*) inside, feeling suffocated under the influence of that excruciating pain, which fact has determined the 4 nomenclatures of ***Shoola*** [2]. Whereas an infant with colic pain only expresses continuous cry. Detailed etiopathogenesis about 8 types of ***Shoola*** [3], and the clue for the management of ***Udarashoola*** described in Ayurvedic classics, are referred to analyze the disease [4]. There is no similar type of ***Shoola*** found in classics to describe as per infantile colic; however, some references of ***Udarashoola*** given here for easy understanding. The gross

features of **Udara Shoola** are mentioned as **Koshte Vibanda** (constipation), **Vamathu** (vomiting), **Sthana Damsha** (biting of the breast), **Antrakujana** (gurgling sound in the abdomen), **Adhmana** (flatulence), **Pristanamana** (bending back), and **Jathara Unnamana** (elevation of the abdomen) [5].

Infantile colic is a strange and perplexing illness. Every year, it is estimated that 22.5% of all babies suffer from colic. Infantile colic is described as uncontrollable weeping in newborns aged 0-3 months for more than three hours per day, more than three days per week, for three weeks or longer. It is most common in the afternoon and evening [6]. Approximately 47 percent of infantile colic

cases resolved by the age of three months, another 41 percent resolved by the age of six months, and the remaining 12 percent resolved between the ages of six and twelve months [7]. Therefore, there was a need to check the effectiveness of Ayurvedic drug compositions over **Udarashoola**, which will reduce the symptoms of colic without its regression, with negligible side effects.

The reason behind the selection of **Vyoshadi Yoga**, the ingredients of **Vyoshadi Yoga** are mentioned in **Arogya Raksha Kalpadrumah** [8], which is indicated for **Udarashoola**, having main ingredients as depicted in table no.1, with eight main drugs, each with 30 grams.

Table 1: Ingredients of formulation and its properties

Drug Name	Rasa	Virya	Vipāka	Guṇa	Action	Gana
Śuṅṭhī (<i>Zingiber officinalis</i> Roxb., Roots)[9]	Kaṭu	Uṣṇa	Mādhur a	Laghu & Snigdha	Dīpana, Pācana, Śothaghna	Dīpaniya, Śūlapraśamana (Ch.S.); Pippalyādi, Trikatu (Su.S.)
Marīca (<i>Piper nigrum</i> Linn., Fruits)[10]	Kaṭu	Uṣṇa	Kaṭu	Laghu, Tikṣṇa	Dīpana, Pācana, Vātānuloma na, Krimighna, Jvaraghna	Dīpaniya, Śūlapraśamana (Ch.); Pippalyādi, Tryuṣaṇa (Su.S.)
Pippalī (<i>Piper longum</i> Linn., Fruits)[11]	Kaṭu	Anuṣṇa	Mādhur a	Laghu, Snigdha, Tikṣṇa	Kaphavātaś āmaka, Dīpana, Rasāyana	Dīpaniya, Śūlapraśamana (Ch.); Pippalyādi, Tryuṣaṇa, Āmlakyādi (Su.S.)
Ajamodā (<i>Carum roxburghianu m</i> DC. Craib,	Kaṭu, Tikta	Uṣṇa	Kaṭu	Laghu, Tikṣṇa, Snigdha	Dīpanī, Hṛdya, Basti-roga- rujāpaha	Śūlapraśamana, Dīpaniya (Ch.)

Fruits)[12]						
Jiraka (<i>Cuminum cyminum</i> Linn., Bija)[13]	Tikta, Kaṭu, Mādhura	Uṣṇa	Kaṭu	Laghu, Tikṣṇa, Snigdha	Pācana, Vedanāsthā paka, Grāhī	Śūlapraśamana (Ch.); Pippalyādi (Su.S.)
Kṛṣṇa Jiraka (<i>Carum bulbocastanum</i> , Bija)[14]	Kaṭu	Uṣṇa	Kaṭu	Laghu, Snigdha	Pācana, Vedanāsthā paka, Grāhī	—
Hiṅgu (<i>Ferula foetida</i> , Nirvāsa)[15]	Kaṭu	Uṣṇa	Kaṭu	Laghu, Tikṣṇa, Snigdha	Dīpana, Pācana, Rucikara, Anulomana, Jantughna	Dīpaniya (Ch.); Pippalyādi, Uṣākādi (Su.S.)
Saindhava (<i>Sodium chloridum</i> , Salt)[16]	Lavaṇa	Uṣṇa	Mādhura or Kaṭu	Guru, Snigdha, Tikṣṇa	Trṣoghna, Avidāhī, Agnidīpana	—

Objective

To study the effect of **Vyoshadi Yoga** in relieving **Udarashoola** with respect to infantile colic.

Materials and Methods

Case Presentation

Patient Information:

A 3-month-old male infant, exclusively breastfed, presented with the following:

- A 10-day history of excessive, irritable crying episodes lasting 3–4 hours daily, primarily occurring in the late afternoon and evening.

Clinical Findings:

- Physical examination revealed abdominal distension, facial flushing, and signs of discomfort upon palpation of the abdomen.

History of Past Illness:

- No history of any major illness or surgery.

Drug History:

- No known drug history.

Family History:

- No history of consanguineous marriage.

Birth History:

1. **Antenatal:** Non-specific.
2. **Natal:** Full-term normal delivery at the hospital. The baby cried immediately after birth.
 - Birth weight: 2.6 kg.
 - No NICU admission.
 - No signs or symptoms of hyperbilirubinemia.

Feeding History:

- Exclusively breastfed from the first feed.

Immunization History:

- Vaccinations administered according to age.

General Examination:

- **Anthropometry:**
 - Height: 56 cm
 - Weight: 5.4 kg
 - Head circumference: 40 cm
 - Chest circumference: 32 cm
 - Mid-arm circumference: 12 cm
 - Pulse: 110 beats per minute
 - Temperature: 96.5°F
 - Respiratory Rate: 32/min
- **Ahara:** Exclusively on breast milk (Ksheerapavastha).

Systemic Examination:

- **Respiratory System (RS):** AEBE (As Expected By Examination) clear.
- **Cardiovascular System (CVS):** S1, S2 normal, no murmurs.
- **Central Nervous System (CNS):** Conscious, active.
- **Per Abdomen (P/A):** Tender with gaseous distension.
- **Sleep:** Disturbed, with frequent crying episodes.
- **Urine:** 7–8 times per day, without complaints.
- **Stool:** 1–2 times per day, without complaints.

Developmental Milestones:

- Achieved as per age.

Diagnosis:

Based on the clinical presentation and Ayurvedic principles, the infant was diagnosed with *Udarashoola*.

Diagnostic Criteria (According to Ayurveda):

Signs and symptoms of *Udarashoola* mentioned in Ayurvedic classics, particularly in the *Kashyapa Samhita*, include:

- **Stana Dwesha:** Refusal to feed.
- **Rodana:** Excessive crying.
- **Udara Stabdhatta:** Abdominal distension.
- **Mukhasweda:** Sweating over the face.
- **Shaitya Prachiti:** Cold extremities.

Dosage and Administration:

- **Form:** Choorṇa (powder) form.
- **Dose:** 125 mg per dose.
- **Anupana:** Mixed with honey.
- **Timing:** Administer twice daily after feeding, for 14 days.

Assessment Criteria:

Assessment was made based on the improvement in clinical features, using suitable gradations of both subjective and objective clinical features before and after treatment.

Subjective Criteria:

1. **Pain:**
 - Frequency of pain in 3-hour duration.

- Duration of pain.
- 2. Sleep:**
 - Duration of sleep in a 24-hour period.
 - Frequency of interruption in a 24-hour period.
- 3. Bloating of Abdomen.**
- 4. Excessive Cry.**

Objective Criteria:

- 1. Skin:**
 - Warm, cold/clammy, and temperature with sweating.
- 2. Gurgling Sounds in Abdomen (Stethoscope):**
 - Frequency, duration, and intensity

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

SN.	CLINICAL FEATURES	BT (DAY 0)	AT (DAY14)	% OF IMPROVEMENT
1	frequency of pain in 3 hrs duration	5 episodes	2 episodes	66%
2	Duration of spasm (total/min in 3 hours)	60 min	20min	67%
3	Sleep duration in 24hr period	11 hr	12.5 hr	14%
4	Frequency of interruption in 24hr period	6 times	2 times	67%
5	Skin on Touch rigidity/distension scale: 0–3)	2	0.5	75%
6	Frequency of Gurgling sound in the abdomen(number/day)	8	3	62%
7	Duration of Gurgling sound in the abdomen(total/min/day)	120 min	40min	67%

- **Pain frequency and spasm duration** reduced by approximately **66–67%** by day 14
- **Abdominal symptoms**—gurgling frequency and duration—dropped by **over 60%**, indicating improved gut comfort.
- **Sleep improvements** ~14% longer sleep, 67% fewer awakenings
- **Abdominal rigidity** notably eased, pointing to effective

pacification of *Vata* and resolution of abdominal congestion.

Discussion

According to Ayurveda, *Vata Dosh* is the chief factor in the pathogenesis of *Udarashoola*, which clinically correlates with infantile colic. The inherent properties of *Vata*, namely *Chala* (mobile) and *Ruksha* (dry), when aggravated, disrupt normal digestion and intestinal movement, leading to symptoms such as abdominal distension, excessive crying, and disturbed sleep.

In neonates, **Mandagni** (impaired digestive fire) contributes to the formation of **Ama**

(undigested toxic byproducts) and causes **Strotodushti** (blockage in body channels), further aggravating colic-like symptoms. From a modern perspective, immature gut flora, improper digestion of breast milk or formula, food sensitivities, and inadequate burping can contribute to colic and gas buildup, mirroring Ayurvedic pathogenesis.

Probable Mode of Action of Vyoshadi Yoga

The synergistic effect of the formulation is attributable to the **Rasapanchaka** (*Rasa, Guna, Virya, Vipaka, Karma*) of its constituents, which collectively exert the following actions:

- **Agnideepana** (stimulation of digestive fire)
- **Amapachana** (elimination of undigested toxins)
- **Vatanulomana** (regulation of Vata movement)
- **Shulaprashamana** (pain relief)
- **Krimighna** (anti-parasitic)
- **Rasayana** (rejuvenative)

Each component contributes uniquely to the **Vata**-pacifying and digestion-enhancing properties of the formulation:

- **Shunthi**: With **Ushna Virya** and **Katu Rasa**, it activates **Agni**, reduces **Mandagni**, and acts as a

carminative. Its **Tikshna Guna** enables **Amapachana**, relieving flatulence and abdominal discomfort.

- **Maricha**: Increases **Agni**, removes **Sanchita Doshas**, and supports **Strotoshodhana**. It is particularly effective in **Agnimandya**, **Ajirna**, and **Adhmana**.
- **Pippali**: Exhibits **Rasayana** and **Shulaprashamana** effects while promoting **Deepana** and **Strotoshodhana**. Its **Madhura Vipaka** ensures nourishing effects on **Rasa Dhatu**, which is vital in infants.
- **Ajmoda**: Its **Katu-Tikta Rasa** and **Ushna Virya** make it potent for **Vatanulomana**, relieving gas and **Adhmana**.
- **Jeeraka & Krishna Jeeraka**: Their **Deepana-Pachana**, **Shulaprashamana**, and **Grahi** properties regulate digestion and ease abdominal tension.
- **Hingu**: Renowned for its **Vata-shamaka**, **Ruchikara**, and **Krimighna** actions, it is effective in **Udarashoola**, **Gulma**, and **Vibandha**.
- **Saindhava Lavana**: Serves as a **Yogavahi**, enhancing the action and absorption of other drugs. Its

Agnideepana and **Sookshma** properties assist in fast-acting digestion and **Vata** regulation.

The **Choorṇa** form, administered with honey as **Anupana**, enhances palatability and bioavailability. Honey, a proven **Yogavahi**, carries the properties of accompanying substances deeper into tissues. It also adds antiseptic, antibacterial, anti-inflammatory, and soothing effects, as confirmed in modern research.

Outcome of Treatment

1. Frequency of Pain Episodes (↓66%)

The significant reduction in pain episodes indicates effective **Vata** pacification and **Shulaprashamana** (pain-alleviating) action of the formulation. Key contributors include:

- **Shunthi**, **Pippali**, and **Maricha** (**Trikatu**) stimulate **Agni**, reducing **Ama** and correcting **Mandagni**, which is the root cause of colic pain.
- **Ajmoda**, **Jeeraka**, and **Krishna Jeeraka** aid in **Vatanulomana**, allowing proper movement of **Vata** and relieving spasmodic episodes.

- **Hingu**, known for its strong carminative (**Vata-reducing**) and **Shulaprashamana** action, directly reduces abdominal spasms.

2. Duration of Spasm (↓67%)

The reduced duration of spasmodic episodes further highlights the role of **Deepana** (digestive stimulant) and **Pachana** (digestive enhancer) herbs in the formula.

- The **Tikshna Guna** of **Maricha** and **Pippali** helps break down accumulated **Ama**, which is a known contributor to pain and spasm.
- The synergy among **Trikatu**, **Hingu**, and **Saindhava** facilitates quicker resolution of abdominal congestion.

3. Sleep Duration (↑14%)

Colic-related sleep disturbances are directly related to abdominal discomfort and pain. Improvement in sleep duration is an indirect but important indicator of overall symptom relief.

- As **Shula** reduces and digestion improves, the

infant's natural biological rhythms are restored.

- The **Snigdha** (unctuous) and **Laghu** (light) properties of several ingredients promote internal balance, enhancing restfulness.
- Additionally, honey, as an **Anupana**, provides a mild sedative and soothing effect, aiding sleep.

4. Sleep Interruptions (↓67%)

Reduction in nighttime crying and awakenings shows significant symptomatic relief from bloating and pain.

- The role of **Vatanulomana** dravyas like **Ajmoda**, **Krishna Jeeraka**, and **Hingu** is prominent here.
- **Vyoshadi Yoga**, by clearing **Vata Sanchaya** in the gastrointestinal tract, promotes uninterrupted sleep, as reflected by the outcome.

5. Abdominal Rigidity/Distension on Touch (↓75%)

The substantial improvement in abdominal tension suggests the

successful clearing of gas and **Ama**.

- **Hingu** acts as a potent **Vata-shamaka**, while **Saindhava Lavana**, due to its **Sookshma** and **Srotoshodhana** properties, enhances deep penetration of other drugs.
- This directly contributes to softening of the abdomen, alleviating stiffness, and calming intestinal spasms.

6. Frequency of Gurgling Sounds (↓62%)

This reduction indicates better digestive activity and gut motility regulation.

- Excessive bowel sounds suggest **Ama** fermentation or improper peristalsis, which are corrected through **Deepana-Pachana** and **Vatanulomana** actions.
- **Jeeraka** and **Ajmoda**, being **Grahi** and **Vatanulomaka**, normalize the movement of **Vata** in the GI tract.

7. Duration of Gurgling Sounds (↓67%)

The shortened duration of gurgling confirms improved gut stabilization.

- Herbs like **Krishna Jeeraka** and **Shunthi**, with their **Tikshna** and **Snigdha Gunas**, help balance intestinal movement and reduce colic-like fermentation.
- Collectively, they restore **Samagni** (balanced digestion), preventing prolonged GI hyperactivity.

Conclusion

The clinical findings of this study demonstrate that **Vyoshadi Yoga** is an effective and safe Ayurvedic intervention in the management of **Udarashoola** (infantile colic). The formulation showed significant improvement across key clinical parameters such as pain frequency and duration, abdominal bloating, gurgling sounds, sleep disturbances, and abdominal rigidity. Its therapeutic effects

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can be attributed to its **Agnideepana** (digestive stimulant), **Amapachana** (detoxifying), **Vatanulomana** (carminative), and **Shulaprashamana** (pain-relieving) actions, owing to the synergistic properties of its ingredients.

Administered with honey as **Anupana**, **Vyoshadi Yoga** proved to be not only palatable and acceptable for infants but also enhanced the absorption and bioactivity of the formulation. This intervention offers a cost-effective, natural, and holistic approach in treating functional abdominal pain in infants, especially when aligned with Ayurvedic principles.

Further multi-center randomized controlled trials with larger sample sizes and longer follow-ups are recommended to validate these findings and establish **Vyoshadi Yoga** as a standardized Ayurvedic remedy in pediatric practice.

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